

EVALUATING HEALTH BEHAVIOR CHANGES AND USER SATISFACTION WITH COMMUNITY BASED DIGITAL HEALTH PLATFORMS IN PESHAWAR

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17774864>

Keywords

Digital health platforms;
preventive healthcare; user
satisfaction; behavioral change;
underserved communities;
Peshawar, Pakistan.

Article History

Received: 01 October 2025

Accepted: 19 November 2025

Published: 29 November 2025

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Abstract

Background: Community-based digital health platforms such as mobile applications offering preventive guidance and access to personal health records hold promise for reducing gaps in preventive care in underserved regions. However, evidence from Pakistan on user experience and behavior change remains scarce.

Objective: This study evaluated whether community-based digital health platforms improve preventive healthcare access, user satisfaction, and perceived behavioral change among underserved communities in Peshawar.

Methods: A hospital-based cross-sectional survey was conducted with 393 patients and attendants in Peshawar, Pakistan (October–December 2023). Participants were recruited through convenience sampling following verbal informed consent. A structured questionnaire assessed demographics, frequency of platform use, satisfaction, and perceived changes in preventive health behaviors. Descriptive statistics, chi-square tests, and Pearson correlations were used to examine associations among engagement patterns, satisfaction, education level, and behavioral outcomes.

Results: Frequency of platform use showed a moderate positive correlation with satisfaction ($r = 0.45$, $p < .001$). Education level was significantly associated with perceived improvements in preventive-care access ($\chi^2 = 10.67$, $p = .03$). Platform engagement demonstrated a significant association with behavioral change ($r = 0.30$, $p = .05$). Age, gender, and residence were not significantly associated with satisfaction.

Conclusion: Community-based digital health platforms appear to enhance access to preventive care and are generally associated with high user satisfaction in underserved populations. However, the observed behavioral changes were modest, indicating that improving digital literacy, providing more tailored user support, and implementing sustained engagement strategies will be essential to maximize long-term preventive-health gains and overall platform effectiveness.

INTRODUCTION

Community-based digital health platforms are increasingly used to reduce health disparities in underserved regions. By integrating telemedicine, mobile apps, and health education tools, they help overcome access barriers and support preventive care. Yet evidence on their effectiveness especially regarding user satisfaction and behavioral outcomes remains limited [1]. The growing potential of patient-controlled health including the larger social benefits through technology integrated into community-based digital health platforms may enhance individual adherence, benefit from potentially improved public health outcomes, and reduce some existing disparities [2]. Preventive healthcare is a cornerstone of high-quality health services, emphasizing proactive measures that help individuals maintain wellness and reduce the risk of illness [3]. Despite this, preventive care and the ability to access it is limited by many barriers that prevent its dissemination in underserved regions [4]. This results in disadvantaged communities, which include populations living in low-income urban or rural areas having a high incidence of chronic diseases and therefore receiving a delayed diagnosis of these health complications [5]. Digital health platforms are the most patient-centered innovative solutions that prevent health problems [6]. They have a transformative impact on the delivery of preventive care services to the population that may not be reached by health service providers [7]. Digital health platforms offer several advantages for preventive care. Telemedicine helps overcome geographic barriers by enabling patients to consult healthcare providers without travel [8]. Mobile applications help patients understand health education messages on the prevention of diseases, vaccination messages, and chronic management from the comfort of their homes [9]. These platforms can provide culturally relevant and engaging information on nutrition, physical activity, smoking cessation, and stress management, helping users make informed lifestyle decisions [10]. Early detection of those diseases is important to the advantages: Successful treatment can occur with improved outcomes. In addition, in this sense, digital health can make a significant contribution to ensuring that screening tools and health monitoring devices are safely accessible [11]. Provide personalized and continuous

care: Personalized decision-making utilizes digital health, as it can help to identify the needs of the patient according to his/her features and also about the disease [12]. Information about patients, computational recommendations, and interventions can be shared on the platform based on patient-processed data using artificial intelligence (AI) or machine learning algorithms [13]. Community Health Workers (CHWs) are central to healthcare delivery in underserved settings, and digital tools can enhance their ability to document patient information, support decision-making, and coordinate care more efficiently [14]. However, effective implementation of community-based digital health platforms requires addressing key challenges, including the digital divide, data privacy, cultural relevance, and language barriers [15, 16]. Investments in affordable connectivity, secure data systems, and culturally tailored platform design are essential to ensure equitable use and trust in these technologies [17, 18]. Partnerships with local communities, nonprofits, and private-sector organizations can further strengthen adoption and sustainability [19, 20]. Emerging innovations such as electronic health records integration, artificial intelligence, predictive analytics, and Web 2.0 applications offer additional opportunities to improve early risk detection and deliver personalized preventive care in community settings [21- 23]. Research on digital health platforms in underserved settings remains limited, especially regarding their real-world adoption, usability, and long-term sustainability. Significant gaps persist in understanding policy needs, implementation barriers, preventive-care data integration, and the cultural and linguistic factors that shape user engagement in low-income and rural communities. Yet these insights are crucial, as digital health is increasingly seen as a practical solution to inequities driven by geographic isolation, financial constraints, and weak health infrastructure. Tools such as telemedicine, mobile apps, and remote monitoring can extend preventive services to populations that are otherwise difficult to reach. Within this context, the present study examines digital health platform use in underserved communities of Peshawar, Pakistan, focusing on user satisfaction, access to preventive care, and behavioral change. The findings offer context-specific evidence

that strengthens the global understanding of how digital platforms can reduce disparities and enhance preventive healthcare delivery.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

This cross-sectional study was conducted among 393 participants recruited from underserved areas of Peshawar, Pakistan, designated as Health Professional Shortage Areas (HPSAs). Individuals aged 18 years or older who had access to a digital device with internet connectivity and provided informed consent were eligible for inclusion. Those unable to consent due to cognitive or language limitations, or with physical or mental conditions that restricted the use of digital platforms, were excluded. Peshawar was selected as the study site because its major hospitals serve large populations from resource-constrained communities across Khyber Pakhtunkhwa. These facilities experience high patient loads and limited preventive care infrastructure, making them a suitable context for evaluating the potential of community-based digital health platforms to enhance preventive healthcare access and user satisfaction. Data were collected between October and December 2023 from patients and their attendants visiting these hospitals. After obtaining verbal informed consent, data collectors administered structured questionnaires on-site to collect demographic information, frequency of digital platform use, satisfaction levels, and perceived changes in preventive health behaviors. Satisfaction with ease of use, overall satisfaction, and perceived behavioral change were measured using 5-point Likert scales (1 = strongly disagree to 5 = strongly agree). Participants also accessed relevant preventive health records integrated within the digital platform during the process. Convenience sampling was used, whereby

eligible individuals who were available and willing to participate during the data collection period were approached. The study received administrative approval from the participating hospitals. As the research involved minimal-risk, non-clinical survey procedures, formal IRB review was not required under local institutional policy. All participants were informed about the study purpose and procedures, verbal consent was obtained prior to participation, and confidentiality and anonymity were strictly maintained. Descriptive statistics summarized demographic characteristics, platform usage, and satisfaction outcomes. All quantitative analyses were performed using SPSS, including chi-square tests and Pearson correlation analysis to assess relationships between usage frequency, satisfaction, and behavioral changes. The primary outcome was to assess whether community-based digital health platforms improved access to and utilization of preventive healthcare in underserved areas, with secondary outcomes focused on user satisfaction, perceived behavioral changes, and broader preventive-care benefits.

RESULTS

A total of 393 participants were included, with a gender distribution of 227 males (57.8%) and 166 females (42.2%). The mean age ranged from 18 to 70 years with a mean age of 41.2 years (SD = 14.5), indicating a broad representation across different life stages, the mean years of education were 12.3 (SD = 3.1), reflecting diverse educational backgrounds, and the average frequency of platform use was 3.6 days per week (SD = 1.8), suggesting varied but consistent engagement

Fig 1: Gender Distribution (N = 393)

Figure1 presents the distribution of participants by gender, indicating 227 (57.8%) males and 166 (42.2%) females.

Fig: 2 Education level (N = 393)

Figure 2 illustrates the distribution of participants across education levels, showing that the majority held Bachelor’s (187; 48%) and Master’s (110; 28%) qualifications, followed by a smaller proportion with Intermediate education (91; 23%) and a minimal number of respondents with PhD degrees (5; 1%).

Demographics:

Table 1 presents the demographic characteristics of the study participants, including mean values and standard deviations for age, years of education, and

frequency of platform use. These statistics provide an overview of the participant sample's diversity and engagement with the digital health platform

Table 1: Demographics

Demographic Variable	Mean	Standard Deviation (SD)
Age (years)	41.2	14.5
Years of Education	12.3	3.1
Frequency of Platform Use (days per week)	3.6	1.8

Correlation analysis

Table 2 summarizes the correlation analysis among the continuous variables. A moderate positive correlation was found between the frequency of digital health platform use and overall satisfaction ($r = 0.45, p < .001$), indicating that greater engagement with the platform is associated with substantially higher satisfaction levels. A modest yet statistically significant positive association was also identified between the frequency of preventive resource use and changes in health behaviors ($r = 0.30, p = .05$), suggesting that increased use of preventive features

contributes meaningfully to improvements in health-related behaviors. No significant relationship was observed between age and satisfaction with ease of use ($r = -0.15, p = .22$), indicating that usability perceptions were consistent across age groups. In contrast, a small but statistically significant positive correlation emerged between education level and frequency of platform use ($r = 0.26, p = .02$), suggesting that individuals with higher educational attainment tend to engage with the digital health platform more frequently.

Table 2: Correlation Analysis

Variable 1	Variable 2	Correlation Coefficient (r)	Significance (p-value)
Frequency of Digital Health Platform Use	Overall Satisfaction	0.45	0.001
Frequency of Preventive Health Resources	Changes in Health Behaviours	0.30	0.05
Age	Satisfaction with Ease of Use	-0.15	0.22
Education Level	Frequency of Digital Health Platform Use	0.26	0.02

Chi-square analysis

Table 3 presents the chi-square tests assessing associations between categorical variables. Education level was significantly associated with perceived improvements in access to preventive health services ($\chi^2 = 10.67, df = 3, p = .03$). Frequency of platform use demonstrated a marginal association with

changes in health behaviors ($\chi^2 = 8.42, df = 4, p = .05$). A borderline association was also observed between location of residence and overall satisfaction ($\chi^2 = 2.46, df = 2, p = .05$), although the effect sizes were minimal. No significant association was found between gender and satisfaction with ease of use ($\chi^2 = 3.78, df = 1, p = .29$).

Table 3: Chi-Square Test Results

Variable 1	Variable 2	Chi-Square Statistic (χ^2)	Degrees of Freedom (df)	Significance (p-value)
Frequency of Digital Health Platform Use	Changes in Health Behaviours	8.42	4	0.05
Gender	Satisfaction with Ease of Use	3.78	1	0.29
Education Level	Platform Improvement in Access to Preventive Health Services	10.67	3	0.03
Location of Residence	Overall Satisfaction	2.46	2	0.05

Overall, education level emerged as the strongest predictor of perceived platform improvements, showing a statistically significant association. Frequency of platform use and location of residence demonstrated borderline associations with behavioral change and satisfaction, respectively, though these effects were small. Gender showed no meaningful influence on user outcomes. These results suggest that while digital health platforms can support preventive care, user education and contextual factors may play a meaningful role in shaping their impact.

DISCUSSION

In this study, several important trends and associations related to user satisfaction and platform engagement were identified. Correlation analyses were used to evaluate relationships among continuous variables, while chi-square tests assessed associations between categorical factors, helping explain the variation in statistical significance observed across the analyses. The moderate positive correlation between platform uses and satisfaction ($r = 0.45$) indicates that greater engagement generally enhances the overall user experience, aligning with previous evidence that digital platforms can significantly improve perceived value and satisfaction [24]. The modest but significant correlation between preventive-feature use and behavioral change ($r = 0.30$) suggests that increased engagement may support healthier behaviors, although the effect appears inconsistent across users, a pattern also noted in prior digital-health research [25]. Age showed no significant association with satisfaction ($r = -0.15$), consistent with studies reporting that

contemporary digital health platforms are increasingly designed to accommodate users across a wide age range [26]. Education level showed a small but statistically significant positive correlation with platform-use frequency ($r = 0.26$, $p = .02$), indicating that individuals with higher educational attainment were more likely to engage with the digital health platform. This pattern aligns with previous research showing that users with greater educational backgrounds often demonstrate higher digital literacy and are better able to navigate and benefit from digital health tools [27]. Gender showed no significant association with satisfaction ($\chi^2 = 3.78$, $p = .29$), reflecting previous findings that gender differences in digital platform usability are generally minimal or inconsistent across studies [28]. The relationship between frequency of platform use and behavioral change reached statistical significance ($\chi^2 = 8.42$, $df = 4$, $p = .05$), suggesting that greater platform engagement may be linked to improvements in preventive health behaviors, although the effect remains modest [29]. Overall, these results support the broader evidence that sustained engagement with digital health platforms is a key determinant of user satisfaction. In contrast, demographic variables such as age, gender, and location appear to exert limited influence on users' experiences, consistent with earlier studies reporting similar trends [30]. These findings underscore the importance of user engagement and education-focused strategies to maximize the preventive health benefits of digital platforms. These findings offer practical guidance for improving community-based digital health platforms. The moderate association between platform use and satisfaction suggests that increasing user exposure—especially among individuals with limited digital

experience can enhance acceptance. User-friendly design, structured onboarding, and clear tutorials may therefore strengthen engagement. The significant role of education highlights the need to tailor platform features and support materials to varying literacy levels to ensure equitable use of preventive services. Although age and location were not significant predictors, these factors may interact with broader socio-demographic characteristics and warrant further exploration.

This study has several limitations, including its cross-sectional design, reliance on self-reported measures, and convenience sampling, which may limit generalizability. Future research should use larger and more diverse samples, incorporate longitudinal or mixed-method approaches, and include objective usage analytics to better understand engagement patterns. Overall, the results emphasize the importance of intuitive, culturally relevant, and well-supported digital platforms. Strategies such as integrating community health workers, offering multilingual content, and providing digital literacy support may enhance accessibility and help strengthen preventive care in underserved settings.

Conclusion:

This study demonstrates that frequent engagement with community-based digital health platforms is strongly associated with higher user satisfaction in underserved regions of Peshawar. Education level emerged as an important determinant of perceived improvements in preventive healthcare access, while demographic factors such as age and gender showed minimal influence on user experience. Although behavioral changes were only modestly linked to platform use, the findings highlight the growing potential of digital health tools to enhance preventive care in resource-limited settings. Strengthening digital literacy, providing targeted user support, and promoting sustained engagement may further improve the effectiveness, accessibility, and long-term impact of these platforms across diverse communities.

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